

Interaction of antibiotic with aminoacyl tRNA synthetase active site : A molecular dynamics simulation study

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Abstract : In the present work we present molecular dynamics simulation study of dimeric seryl tRNA synthetase bound with antibiotic molecule, SB 217452 that targets the active site of the bacterial enzyme and inhibits the protein biosynthesis. The interaction pattern within the active site of the enzyme is compared with the pattern in the active site of the enzyme with the adenylate to understand how the antibiotic acts as competitive inhibitor. Detailed analysis of the population of hydrogen bonds within the active sites bound with antibiotic and bound with adenylate have been carried out and compared. The results of the simulation show that the antibiotic develops hydrogen bonds, not present in the adenylate bound active site which leads to a tightly bound state of the antibiotic. Further, the conformation of the bound antibiotic is such that a reaction analogous to tRNA charging is impossible. The inhibitor molecule (SB 217452) which acts as a transition state analogue, has a higher affinity than the cognate substrate (or the related products) of aminoacylation. The SB 217452 binds to the enzyme more strongly by forming stable interactions with the enzyme. This tight-binding capacity of these transition state analogues allows them to be released slowly from the enzyme. The inhibitor SB 217452 resides within the active site of the enzyme relatively longer and acts as a competitive inhibitor. The present work, for the first time explains the antibiotic action of the SB 217452.

Keywords : Seryl tRNA synthetase, active site, antibiotic.

Introduction

Bacterial infection is a perpetual threat for human¹. One of the many ways to stop the growth of the pathogens is to inhibit the process of translation during protein synthesis. In this regard, different aminoacyl tRNA synthetases (*aaRSs*) have significant potential in the development of new inhibitors and are interesting antibacterial drug targets²⁻⁶. Aminoacyl tRNA synthetases carry out the aminoacylation reaction within their catalytic active site. The reaction, in which the tRNA is charged with its cognate amino acid for subsequent steps of protein biosynthesis, is a vital biochemical reaction driving life processes. Due to its biological importance, the structures of *aaRSs* are studied extensively⁷⁻¹⁷ using various methods such as X-ray crystallography, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) studies, mutation experiments, biochemical methods, kinetic analysis, quantum mechanical calculations, theoretical analysis and classical molecular dynamics (MD)

simulation. However, the molecular level analysis of the systematic development of antibiotics targeting *aaRSs* are relatively few and more studies are required in this direction.

Most inhibitors of *aaRSs* act by competitive binding at the active site where normally the cognate amino acid would bind. Albomycin (also termed as grisein) is a Trojan horse antibiotic^{5,6} which utilizes the siderophore mediated transport mechanism to permeate the membrane permeability barrier. The molecule contains a thioribosyl nucleoside moiety linked to a hydroxamate siderophore through a serine residue. The seryl nucleoside structure (SB 217452) is a potent inhibitor of seryl-tRNA synthetase (SerRS) in the pathogenic bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus*, with a 50% inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of ~8 nM.

SB 217452 inhibitor is an analogue of seryl adenylate in where oxygen atom of sugar ring of seryl ade-

Fig. 1. Structure of Albomycin with the siderophore and the SB 217452.

nylate is substituted by sulfur atom. This molecule acts as SerRS inhibitor and linked with the “Trojan horse antibiotic” albomycin. The structural similarity between SB 217452 and the adenylate is shown in Fig. 2.

In the present work, we investigated the interaction of SB 217452 in the active site of SerRS of *Thermus thermophilus* by comparing it with adenylate bound

active site “SerRS from *Thermus thermophilus* using classical molecular dynamics simulation for a trajectory length of 1 ns. To the best of our knowledge, there is no comparative analysis of the interaction of SB 217452 and adenylate at the active site of SerRS using molecular dynamics simulation. In the next section we present the computational procedure which is followed by results and discussion.

Fig. 2. Comparison of the adenylate and SB 217452. Superimposed structures are optimized at the HF level of theory using 6-31G(d) basis set.

Computational methods :

One of the major problems of studying the interaction is that the crystal structure is unavailable in many cases or truncated. The crystal structure of ³⁵SerRS from *Thermus thermophilus* in complex with tRNA is used as the starting structure of the present work (1SER.pdb)¹⁶. ³⁵SerRS is a homodimer in which each monomer contains 421 amino acids. The structure 1SER.pdb possesses dimeric SerRS bound with one tRNA. The several missing residues in the structure are replaced and the structure is minimized. The N-terminal domain of monomer 1 (residue Glu39 to Leu87) is truncated. The structure of N-terminal domain is taken from another crystal structure (1SES.pdb)¹⁷. The active site of monomer 1 and monomer 2 is vacant. So we docked seryl adenylate to active site of monomer 1 and ATP and serine in the active of monomer 2. We modified tRNA of 1SER.pdb by base mutation by X3-dna software¹⁸ by the deletion of extra bases and addition of truncated regions to maintain the appropriate conformation of tertiary structure of tRNA. The water molecules at the CCA end and chelated Mg²⁺ ions at anticodon loop, long variable loop, D loop, TψC loop and acceptor stem loop along with one spermine molecule near D loop and anticodon loop are docked gradually by AutoDock Vina software¹⁹. Finally, the simulated ³⁵SerRS from *Thermus thermophilus* in complex with tRNA and serine contains two monomers and monomer 1 contains seryl adenylate and monomer 2 contains ATP, serine, two Mg²⁺ ions within the active site, water molecules at the CCA end, chelated Mg²⁺ ions at anticodon loop, long variable loop, D loop, TψC loop and acceptor stem loop, one spermine molecule near D loop and anticodon loop and diffused MgCl₂ (0.01 M). The system was solvated in a rectangular box of TIP3P water molecules with 6 Å distance from protein to the edge of the box in each direction. Total 51800 water molecules are used to form a rectangular box of dimension 116.643 × 104.562 × 166.101 Å³ (2025830.855 Å³) by the Leap program. Total 12 Mg²⁺ ions and corresponding 24 Cl⁻ ions are added to maintain 0.01 M concentration of MgCl₂. Total 83 Na⁺ ions were required to neutralize the whole system. The system contains 174714 atoms.

The zwitterionic SB 217452 is optimized by HF/6-31G(d) method²⁰ and the optimized molecule is docked within active site where seryl adenylate locates. Similar to simulated ³⁵SerRS from *Thermus thermophilus* (as described before), monomer 1 contains zwitterionic SB 217452 molecule and monomer 2 contains ATP, serine, two Mg²⁺ ions within the active site, water molecules at the CCA end, chelated Mg²⁺ ions at anticodon loop, long variable loop, D loop, TψC loop and acceptor stem loop, one spermine molecule near D loop and anticodon loop and 0.01 M diffused MgCl₂. The system was solvated in a rectangular box of TIP3P water molecules with 6 Å distance from protein to the edge of the box in each direction. Total 52598 water molecules are used to form a rectangular box of dimension 116.643 × 105.608 × 166.101 Å³ (2046105.765 Å³) by the Leap program. Total 12 Mg²⁺ ions and corresponding 24 Cl⁻ ions are added to maintain 0.01 M concentration of MgCl₂. Total 83 Na⁺ ions were required to neutralize the whole system. The system contains 174722 atoms.

All simulations are performed using AMBER11 suite of programs^{21,22}. First, all water molecules are energy minimized for 500 steps, while rest of the system was held constrained. This was followed by a 500 steps energy minimization of the overall system without any constraint. Subsequently, isothermal-isobaric (NPT) simulation was run for 100 ps with gradual relaxation of positional restraints over water molecules, whole protein (both monomer), tRNA and substrates for both the systems. This step is followed by simulation run using NPT condition without any restraint. The generalized AMBER Force Field (GAFF)²² is used for substrates and AMBER (leaprc.ff99SB) force field is used for protein molecule. The temperature is maintained at 300 K. Langevin dynamics with collision frequency 1.0 ps⁻¹ is used and pressure is maintained at 1 bar with a relaxation time of 2 ps. All simulations are carried out with a time step of 1 fs. The SHAKE algorithm is used to restrain the bonds linking the heavy atoms and hydrogen atoms. The electrostatic interactions are calculated using the Particle-mesh Ewald sum method. A nonbonded cutoff of 10 Å is used. The trajectories of 1 ns of each of the adenylate and SB 217452 bound states are used for analysis of the results.

Results and discussion

The structures of active sites of ¹⁴SerRS bound with SB 217452 inhibitor and bound with seryl adenylate are shown in Fig. 3a and 3b, respectively from the respective simulated trajectories.

Fig. 3. Structures of the active sites of ¹⁴SerRS bound with (a) SB 217452 and (b) adenylate. Images are prepared from the simulated trajectory at 1 ns in both cases using VMD²⁴.

Comparison of the simulated structures (Fig. 3a and 3b) shows that the binding of the adenylate and SB 217452 inhibitor are closely similar. Earlier quantum mechanical and simulation studies of the interaction between adenylate and active site residues revealed that electrostatic interactions and specifically a network of hydrogen bonds. We compared the network of interactions in case of the inhibitor and adenylate. There are three subsites of the active site, namely ATP binding site, reaction center and Ser binding site, where

the adenylate develops interaction with the active site residues and tRNA to undergo the reaction. In the following we compare the hydrogen bond occupancies between SB 217452 and active site residues and tRNA as well as between adenylate and active site residues and tRNA.

Most significant difference in the hydrogen bonding between SB 217452 and adenylate develop with the β sheets located at the base of the active site. More than 80% occupancy is observed with various atoms of SB 217452 (part of the sugar ring and seryl moiety) with $\beta 6$ and $\beta 7$ which are not observed in the case of adenylate. The occupancies are compared in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy of (a) Glu345 of $\beta 6$ of monomer 1 of dimeric state and (b) Asn378 of $\beta 7$ of monomer 1 of dimeric state. M1 (SB) indicates monomer 1 bound with SB molecule M1 (A) indicates monomer 1 bound with adenylate (shown in Fig. b). In both cases tRNA are bound along with diffused Mg^{2+} ions, as stated in the text.

For the adenylate system there is no hydrogen bond interaction between O ϵ 2 of Glu345 of β 6 and O2' of adenylate. On the other hand, the percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy between O ϵ 2 of Glu345 of β 6 and O2' of SB 217452 molecule for SB 217452 system is 100% for most of the time periods of the trajectory. The percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy between O δ 1 of Asn378 of β 7 and N9' of SB 217452 molecule for the SB 217452 system is almost 100% with a sudden decrease after 750 ps. There is only about 22% occupancy between O δ 1 of Asn378 of β 7 and N10 of adenylate molecule. The percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy between ADN (N10) and Asn378 (N δ 2) is fluctuating below 30% and becomes zero at 700 ps. Other residues also develop interactions with SB 217452 better compared to the adenylate. Such residues are Thr225 of loop 12 and Glu279 of motif 2.

The percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy between O γ 1 of Thr225 of Loop 12 and O8' of SB 217452 molecule for the SB 217452 system is fluctuating above 85% for the time period of 100 ps to 700 ps with a sudden decrease after 700 ps. The percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy between O γ 1 of Thr225 of loop 12 and O9 of adenylate is fluctuating with no hydrogen bond after 400 ps. The percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy between O ϵ 2 of Glu279 of motif 2 and N9' of SB 217452 molecule for SB 217452 system is almost greater than 90% with sudden decreases for the time periods of 651 ps to 700 ps and 751 ps to 800 ps. The percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy between O ϵ 2 of Glu279 of motif 2 and N10 of adenylate for adenylate system is fluctuating within the range of 12.5% to 75%. Again the percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy between O ϵ 2 of Glu279 of motif 2 and O14 of SB 217452 molecule for SB 217452 system and the percentage of hydrogen bond occupancy between O ϵ 2 of Glu279 of motif 2 and O γ of adenylate for adenylate system is almost similar maintaining about 100% occupancy.

Various other residues show similar hydrogen bonding pattern in adenylate bound and SB217452 systems. The hydrogen bond occupancies between the substrates (cognate and SB 217452 inhibitor) and the proximal active site residues are computed and the results are presented in Table 1 for ³⁵SerRS.

Fig. 5. The percentage of hydrogen bond occupancies of (a) Thr225 of loop 12 of monomer 1 of dimeric state and (b) Glu279 of motif 2 of monomer 1. M1 (SB) indicates monomer 1 bound with SB molecule M1 (A) indicates monomer 1 bound with adenylate (shown in Fig. b). In both cases tRNA are bound along with diffused Mg²⁺ ions, as stated in the text.

In the Fig. 6, few atoms are pointed out where major differences in hydrogen bonding occupancies are observed between SB 217452 bound and adenylate bound systems.

It is noted from Table 1 and Fig. 6 that differences in the binding behavior are noted in all three subsites of the active site of SerRS. More than 50% differences in hydrogen bond occupancy (three cases with more than 80% differences) are noted. In contrast, only one hydrogen bond is missing (with less than 80% occupancy) in the ATP binding subsite in the case of SB 217452. This loss of binding is overcompensated by two more hydrogen bonds in the same region with tRNA. There is no hydrogen bond occu-

Table 1. The comparisons of the hydrogen bond occupancies between active site residues of ³⁵SerRS bound with tRNA and cognate substrate (seryl adenylate) and between active site residues of ³⁵SerRS bound with tRNA and SB 217452 inhibitor (indicated as SB)

	Subsite	Interacting atom	Interacting residues	Average hydrogen bond occupancies (%)	Average difference in H-bond occupancy (%)
I	ATP binding subsite	O2' (SB)	Oε2 (Glu345; β6)	99.08	99.08
		O2' (A)	Oε2 (Glu345; β6)	0	
II	Serine binding subsite	N9' (SB)	Oδ1 (Asn378; β7)	93.57	92.48
		N10 (A)	Oδ1 (Asn378; β7)	1.09	
III	Serine binding subsite	N9' (SB)	Oδ1 (Asn378; β7)	93.57	82.1
		N10 (A)	Nδ2 (Asn378; β7)	11.47	
IV	Reaction center	O8' (SB)	Oγ1 (Thr225; Loop 12)	63.05	50.61
		O9 (A)	Oγ1 (Thr225; Loop 12)	12.44	
V	Serine binding subsite	N9' (SB)	Oε2 (Glu279; M2)	96.75	40.05
		N10 (A)	Oε2 (Glu279; M2)	56.7	
VI	Reaction center	O12 (SB)	Nη2 (Arg256; M2L)	33.69	15.68
		O2P (A)	Nη2 (Arg256; M2L)	18.01	
VII	Reaction center	O8' (SB)	Nζ (Lys277; M2)	20.4	15.55
		O9 (A)	Nζ (Lys277; M2)	4.85	
VIII	ATP binding subsite	N9 (SB)	Oε2 (Glu258; M2L)	12.01	6.51
		N6 (A)	Oε2 (Glu258; M2L)	5.5	
IX	Serine binding subsite	N9' (SB)	Oε1 (Glu227; H11)	92.01	1.93
		N10 (A)	Oε1 (Glu227; H11)	90.08	
X	ATP binding subsite	O3' (SB)	Oε2 (Glu345; β6)	99.97	1.77
		O3' (A)	Oε2 (Glu345; β6)	98.2	
XI	Serine binding subsite	O14 (SB)	Oε2 (Glu279; M2)	97.65	-0.24
		Oγ (A)	Oε2 (Glu279; M2)	97.89	
XII	Serine binding subsite	O14 (SB)	Oγ1 (Thr380; β7)	52.85	-5.7
		Oγ (A)	Oγ1 (Thr380; β7)	58.55	
XIII	ATP binding subsite	N9 (SB)	Oε1 (Glu258; M2L)	35.82	-25.25
		N6 (A)	Oε1 (Glu258; M2L)	61.07	
XIV	ATP binding subsite	N9 (SB)	O (Val272; M2L)	10.87	-70.85
		N6 (A)	O (Val272; M2L)	81.72	
XV	ATP binding subsite	O8 (SB)	N4 (C75; tRNA)	70.64	70.64
		N6 (A)	N4 (C75; tRNA)	0	
XVI	Reaction center	O12 (SB)	O2' (A76; tRNA)	40.31	40.31
		O2P (A)	O2' (A76; tRNA)	0	

pancy is observed between adenylate and tRNA. The result indicates that SB 217452 is more tightly bound compared to the adenylate.

The results of the present simulation study explain the basis of inhibitory action of SB 217452 molecule within the active site of SerRS. Although the chemical structure of SB 217452 is analogous with the adenylate, the conformation of former molecule is different

from the adenylate due to the cyclic thioether group (-C-S-C-) present in the former. The nucleoside component of the SB 217452 is composed of a cyclic thioether part. The C_{3'} conformation is such that the proximity of the various molecular segments in adenylate and SB 217452 are different²⁵. Consequently, the hydrogen bond interaction patterns differ in the two cases. It is established from the present simulation that

Fig. 6. Structures of the active sites of ⁶⁶SerRS bound with adenylate (marked as 'A') and bound with SB 217452 (marked as 'SB'). Images are prepared from the simulated trajectory using VMD²⁴.

SB 217452 makes more stable hydrogen bond pattern with the active site residues and tRNA compared to adenylate. In this rigidly bound state of SB 217452 is not in an effective position to transfer the seryl moiety over the tRNA. A look from the simulated geometry of bound adenylate and bound SB 217452 within the active site reveals this. Here we mention the salient points of bound geometry of SB 217452 that inhibits the tRNA charging reaction to take place. The distance between the carbonyl carbon of SB 217452 and O3' atom of the adenine base (A76) of tRNA is larger than that of the adenylate system. The average distance (averaged over the course of 1 ns trajectory) is 5.45 Å in SB 217452 bound system while the same separation is 3.45 Å in adenylate on an average. Consequently, the attack is less feasible for the SB 217452 bound system. This is shown in Fig. 7. There are further significant differences. The His204 residue of loop *f* is in larger distance from the A76 of tRNA in case of SB 217452 bound system compared to the adenylate bound system. The electronegativity of oxygen atom being greater than that of the nitrogen atom, the breakage of -C-N- bond is less probable than the breakage of the -C-O- bond.

In the case of cognate substrates, the favorable interaction between the enzyme and the transition state decreases the energy barrier between the reactants and products. The inhibitor molecule (SB 217452) as a mimic of the transition state is also stabilized by the same (or more) favorable interactions with the enzyme.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Comparison of the reaction center of the active sites of ⁶⁶SerRS bound with (a) cognate substrates and (b) SB 217452. The arrows with cross marks (X) over arrows indicates that the electronic structural change in Fig. b is less likely compared to analogous changes in Fig. a.

As a result, the inhibitor as a transition state analogue can have a higher affinity than the cognate substrate (or the related products) of aminoacylation. The SB 217452 as a transition state analogue binds to the enzyme more strongly by forming stable interactions with the enzyme while mimicking the real transition state. This tight-binding capacity of these transition state analogues allows them to be released slowly from the enzyme. As an average estimate, the release rate for the transition state analogs, bound tightly to the enzyme is greater than 10^3 seconds, while, the lifetime of the real transition state of the enzymatic reaction is nearly 10^{-15} seconds²³. As a result, the SB 217452 can act as potent inhibitor. The tight-binding analogue causes the inhibitor-enzyme system substantial entropic

penalties. The inhibitor SB 217452 resides within the active site of the enzyme relatively longer and acts as a competitive inhibitor.

Conclusions

Summarizing, the present molecular dynamics simulation study of the adenylate and SB 217452 bound dimeric seryl tRNA synthetase shows that the interaction with the transition state analogue is stronger in the inhibitor compared to the adenylate. Detailed analysis of the population of hydrogen bonds within the active sites bound with antibiotic and bound with adenylate have been carried out and compared. The results of the simulation show that the antibiotic develops hydrogen bonds, not present in the adenylate bound active site which leads to a tightly bound state of the antibiotic. Further, the conformation of the bound antibiotic is such that a reaction analogous to tRNA charging is impossible. The inhibitor molecule (SB 217452) which acts as a transition state analogue, has a higher affinity than the cognate substrate (or the related products) of aminoacylation. The SB 217452 binds to the enzyme more strongly by forming stable interactions with the enzyme. This tight-binding capacity of these transition state analogues allows them to be released slowly from the enzyme. The inhibitor SB 217452 resides within the active site of the enzyme relatively longer and acts as a competitive inhibitor. The present work, for the first time explains the antibiotic action of the antibiotic.

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